

CHILD ENLIGHTENMENT AND SPIRITUALITY - THE MAIN FACTOR IN THE WELL-BEING OF THE FAMILY.

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Annotation. In this scientific article educating of high knowledgeable and capability teenager is the main demand of our period in our country are indicated and in this specialty achievements of high effective works that are doing in our country giving us positive results are shown by scientific sources.

Keywords: independence, society, nation, teenager, moral, education, perfect human, Study - education, healthy child, mature generation.

Spiritual perfection is the spiritual purification of a person, the acquisition of moral consciousness and emotions, the perception of an honest and Pure Life, the possession of a solid faith as a supreme goal. It is worth saying that our people have paid special attention to issues of spirituality and morality since ancient times. The "Avesto", a monument to the Zoroastrian doctrine that embodied the knowledge of our ancient ancestors about society, nature, all being, embodied ideas about spirituality. In the Islamic world, this topic is fully, truthfully, holistically illuminated by the fact that every person should mean the creation of a great future of the country, first of all, his own future, the future of his children, his El-land.

President Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev said that " it is more important than ever to focus on spirituality and Enlightenment, moral education, learning of youth, striving for perfection today, when the world is changing rapidly and various new threats and threats rise to stability and the strong development of peoples. It is education and enlightenment that are considered one of the main factors in the well-being of mankind, calling people to goodness, encouraging them to be generous, patient."Therefore, in the center of all our people and our state, what human actions and good intentions, there is a dream to raise a generation in which our children are not inferior to the children of other peoples, to grow up physically and spiritually healthy, to see their happiness and prosperous future. Because only a comprehensively mature generation can cope with the extremely difficult hard trials and difficulties that life puts before us today, master the high goals and milestones that have been pursued.

Today's youth, in addition to working in all areas, is at the forefront of the role of the system of family values, which correctly educate human qualities in achieving spiritual perfection. The elements of initial social experience and social behavior in a person are formed precisely in the family, in the system of family relations. That is why there is a saying in our people that "the bird does what it sees in the nest". That is, the initial molds of personality qualities are obtained in the family, and this mold becomes polished and refined under the influence of other groups in society. Of particular social importance is the study of the talent and abilities of young people, their emergence, their orientation towards Great Goals. Chapter XIV of our main body dedicated to the family 63-, 64-, 65-, 66-, the articles

strengthen the rules that determine the legal basis of the family. Now, there are 32 and a half million inhabitants, about 8 million families, more than 130 nationalities and elat, covering about 9 thousand neighborhoods. The family tests the traditions of the life, marriage of the people, society in itself. He will deliver the good in his bosom to future generations. The family brings up their children and gives them an initial social orientation with the absorption of universal values. With the inclusion of their children in a large stream — society, the family also has its own influence in determining the direction, economy, culture and education of society. That is why in the East the family has long been considered a sacred fortress. This is also evidenced by the "Avesto" from the main sources. In it, the issues of the role of the husband of the family, women in society, the status of the parents in the household are specially noted, annotated in different places with different relationships. The Uzbek people have long been childish, family-friendly. In avesto, Zarathustra says, " O young men and women who are starting a family, I would like to warn you that each of you is zealous in the path of a clean life. Each of you with good behavior and good behavior, action, achieve a hurried and joyful passage of your life!". The Uzbek family, on the other hand, is devoted to their homeland, people, ideas of independence, selfless, independent-minded, wide-worldview, high faith, talented, responsible, spiritual and physically harmonious generation, and the future of adulthood is a guarantee for the survival of the Great Uzbekistan. A highly spiritual parent realizes and adheres to such tasks as the essence of the family, value, duty, responsibility, family duties, the upbringing of a harmonious child in the family, the material maintenance of the family, the maintenance of its tranquility. Through the love of an educated mother in the Family, national ideology is passed down from generation to generation, from person to person. The moral qualities that the mother has are all passed on to the children. Uzbek families are distinguished by their strength, order, childhood, respect for ties of kinship, mekhr-consequence.

Each parent must have a deep understanding of their duties and responsibilities in the family. Such an attitude has a positive effect on the upbringing of a child if there is harmony in the interaction between parents, mutual respect for kindness, shirinsuhanism, care for each other. They give their children true happiness, joy. The proverbs state that " there are three advantages that children inherit from their fathers: politeness, decency and loyalty", " if you want your name to be memorized with respect among the people, give your children a beautiful upbringing, if you look at the constant comfort of the family." Instilling a child in a family environment with love for reading books, leading towards science, timely involvement in labor is also a guarantee of the success of the family. "Whoever stops reading, know that he has also stopped thinking," Danny Didro is right. Vocabulary, the talent for being able to walk in logical observation is, in fact, mutolaa. Because the most basic function and place of a person is determined by Labor, science, beautiful, beautiful morality. The great thinker Joseph khojib inherited the thoughts of purma'no that " if a child is divided into knowing ways, it is necessary to teach him knowledge from an early age." The beginning of the good in the upbringing of a child in the whole family is the tireless work of the child on himself, his search, the study of science, his implementation and honest, correct work. Without a hardworking person achieving spiritual perfection, it is necessary that we raise our dear children in the spirit of patience, perseverance, hard work in the family. Because free citizenship can build a society only educated, qualified, educated people.

President Shavkat Mirziyoev said that " in the 21st century where we live, this issue is really becoming a matter of life-matter. "The more perfect the upbringing, the happier the people live," says the sages. "It is appropriate for the upbringing to be perfect, but it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to arise in this matter." Therefore, it is necessary not to forget about the fact that a way can be found in the human soul through education and upbringing. In the cultivation of children as a harmonious person, success cannot be achieved without connecting school with the family. Therefore, the joint work of the family on education between the school and parents is of great importance. Every parent who understands the fundamental essence of child education seeks to strengthen cooperation between the family and the school. Until the child completes school, the parent must establish close contact with the school, master the lessons of his child, be aware of his behavior, consult with the teacher, the head of the class on issues of upbringing, inform the teacher and the head of the class about what the child is training with after class. In turn, it is necessary that the teacher and the head of the class also convey to the parents information about the child's studies, manners, behavior, self-control at school, jointly solve the problems that arise when the need arises. That is, in the family, the parent should not constantly lose awareness in the upbringing of the child. A parent whose child attends school must remain a member of the school community. The teacher and the head of the class should also establish strong cooperation with the family of their student. The family also has significant parent partnerships with neighborhood activists, labor veterans.

Today, it is precisely such an initiative that our boys and girls, who take a new approach to each issue, are actively involved in the implementation of such comprehensive programs as "youth – future builder", "prosperous village", "prosperous neighborhood", "smart city" within the framework of the action strategy, will undoubtedly please all of us. Each achievement and deficit hike also has its own basis. As part of the analysis of the achievement and the shortcomings allowed, it is advisable to establish promising plans. This action should be reflected in Real life, and not in a dry paper, but simply in a reporting style. That is why the president points out that without efficiency and consequentialism, our efforts are in vain. It is true that the reality of an effective mechanism that works exactly like a clock is only with an impressive mechanism.

It should be noted that the Family Institute has a special place in our independent democratic society. In each family we are raising children with our future, our face, our backrest, our ugliness. The future of that family will be reliable and successful only if favorable conditions are created for the comprehensive maturation of children in the family

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